

Towards testing $(g - 2)_\tau$ in $e^+e^- \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$: radiative corrections and projections for Belle II

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Abstract

The precision measurement of lepton anomalous magnetic moments remains a key avenue for probing physics beyond the Standard Model. While the electron and muon moments are determined with high precision, the tau lepton's short lifetime makes extracting a_τ challenging. The arguably most promising path forward involves utilizing $e^+e^- \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ with a polarized electron beam, as potentially realizable at a SuperKEKB upgrade. Concretely, we construct asymmetry-based observables tailored to the realistic experimental acceptance of Belle II, enabling the determination of tau dipole moments. We present the complete next-to-leading-order QED computation for the fully polarized process, implemented in the Monte-Carlo integrator MCMULE [1].

1 Introduction

Lepton anomalous magnetic moments, a_ℓ , have long served as precision probes of the Standard Model (SM) [2, 3]. While a_e measurements have reached 10^{-13} [4], BSM interpretations are currently hindered by discrepancies in α from atom interferometry [5, 6]. For a_μ , the recent Fermilab update improved the precision to 1.45×10^{-10} [7], yet the theory prediction remains under scrutiny [8, 9], with the aim of matching the experimental precision over the next years.

In principle, sensitivity to BSM physics scales with the lepton mass, rendering a_τ an attractive probe despite its extremely short lifetime. Improving constraints on a_τ is crucial for disentangling the flavor and chirality structure of new physics via the interplay of all lepton moments [10–14]. However, LEP [15–19] and LHC [20–23] constraints remain orders of magnitude away from the precision of the SM prediction [24–27]. While a precision $\mathcal{O}(10^{-6})$ required for meaningful BSM tests [28] appears elusive at hadron colliders [29–36], Belle II offers a potential path via polarized electron beams [37–39]. Unlike absolute cross-section measurements [40–45], polarization enables the construction of asymmetries [46, 47] that isolate dipole moments while suppressing systematic uncertainties.

While initial two-loop studies [28] and projections [38, 39] suggest a precision of 10^{-5} is achievable at SuperKEKB, strategies relying on lower Υ resonances are hindered by continuum backgrounds [48]. Extending this sensitivity to the 10^{-6} level necessitates further advances in statistics and energy calibration. Crucially, however, the success of this high-precision program depends on analyzing continuum pairs and incorporating full radiative corrections beyond simple form factors. In this work, we address this gap by implementing these corrections into the Monte-Carlo integrator MCMULE to project sensitivity under realistic kinematical cuts.

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2 Methodology and calculation

We analyze the scattering process $e^+(p_1)e^-(p_2) \rightarrow \tau^+(q_1)\tau^-(q_2)\{\gamma(q_3)\}$ considering the full mass dependence of both the electron and the τ lepton. The calculation incorporates the complete NLO QED corrections, including virtual vertex corrections, vacuum polarization, box diagrams, and real photon emission. Regularization of ultraviolet (UV) and infrared (IR) divergences is performed using the four-dimensional formulation of the FDH scheme (FDF) [49], with renormalization carried out in the on-shell scheme. The resulting amplitudes, retaining polarization vectors for all leptons, have been implemented in MCMULE [50–52]. This framework utilizes the FKS ^{ℓ} scheme [53–55] for IR subtraction and next-to-soft (NTS) stabilization [56, 57] to handle numerical instabilities in real–virtual matrix elements. For the electrons, we assume longitudinal polarization along the beam axis, while retaining arbitrary spin configurations for the τ leptons.

3 $e^+e^- \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ cross section and asymmetries

3.1 Form factor decomposition

We employ the canonical decomposition for the QED form factors of the electromagnetic current

$$\langle p_2 | j^\mu | p_1 \rangle = e \bar{u}(p_2) \left[\gamma^\mu F_1(s) + \frac{i\sigma^{\mu\nu} q_\nu}{2m_\ell} F_2(s) + \frac{\sigma^{\mu\nu} q_\nu \gamma_5}{2m_\ell} F_3(s) \right] u(p_1), \quad (1)$$

where $q = p_2 - p_1$ denotes the momentum transfer. We omit the anapole form factor $F_4(s)$ as it is not the primary focus of this study. In the static limit $s \rightarrow 0$, $F_1(0) = 1$ reduces to the charge, while F_2 and F_3 identify with the anomalous magnetic dipole moment and the electric dipole moment (EDM), respectively

$$F_2(0) = a_\ell, \quad F_3(0) = \frac{2m_\ell}{e} d_\ell. \quad (2)$$

In an EFT framework, BSM effects are parameterized by a Wilson coefficient C_R^ℓ , which shifts the dipole moments according to

$$a_\ell^{\text{BSM}} = -\frac{4m_\ell}{e} \text{Re} C_R^\ell, \quad d_\ell^{\text{BSM}} = -2 \text{Im} C_R^\ell. \quad (3)$$

In the regime of heavy new physics ($\Lambda_{\text{BSM}}^2 \gg s$), these corrections primarily modify the real parts of the form factors $F_{2,3}(s)$ and reduce them to their SM expectations shifted by the BSM terms in Eq. (3). Isolating these real parts from the dominant F_1 contribution requires longitudinal and transverse asymmetries enabled by polarized beams. Conversely, light new physics may induce non-negligible imaginary parts in $F_{2,3}(s)$, which can be accessed via the normal asymmetry even with unpolarized beams and is thus already accessible at Belle II today [58, 59].

3.2 Dipole moment extraction via asymmetry-based observables

We investigate the process $e^+e^- \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ followed by the subsequent semileptonic decay channels $\tau^\pm \rightarrow h^\pm \nu_\tau$ ($h^\pm = \pi^\pm, \rho^\pm, \dots$), as these decays enable the reconstruction of the τ production plane and flight direction [60, 61]. In the narrow-width approximation (NWA), the production factorizes from the decay, allowing us to restrict the calculation to the cross section of $e^+e^- \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$. Limiting the analysis to direct s -channel diagrams while retaining the full

structure of the τ electromagnetic form factors, the differential cross section is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = & \frac{\alpha^2 \beta_\tau}{4s\beta_e} \left[|F_1|^2 \left(2 - \beta_\tau^2 + \beta_e^2 \beta_\tau^2 \cos^2 \theta \right) + |F_2|^2 - |F_3|^2 \right. \\ & \left. + (|F_2|^2 + |F_3|^2) \gamma_\tau^2 (1 - \beta_e^2 \beta_\tau^2 \cos^2 \theta) + 4\text{Re}(F_1 F_2^*) + \frac{|F_1 + F_2|^2}{\gamma_e^2} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where β_ℓ and γ_ℓ denote the velocity and Lorentz factor of lepton ℓ , respectively, and θ represents the scattering angle. Although the total cross section is formally sensitive to the magnetic form factors $F_{2,3(s)}$, extracting dipole moments from this observable is challenging; achieving an accuracy of 10^{-5} – 10^{-6} has been shown to be unfeasible primarily due to limiting systematic uncertainties [40, 42]. Consequently, we turn to asymmetry-based observables as proposed in Ref. [46], which exploits the spin information of the τ^\pm given by the spin vectors s_\pm and the electron helicity λ . These observables, measurable once polarized beams become available, offer a significant advantage as systematic uncertainties largely cancel. This makes a precision of 10^{-5} a realistic prospect, while reaching the 10^{-6} level would require increased statistics and higher precision measurements of the fundamental masses m_τ and $M_{\Upsilon(1S)}$ [62].

3.3 Asymmetries for imaginary parts

In the absence of electron beam polarization ($\lambda = 0$), only the imaginary parts of the form factors are accessible via the linearly spin-dependent cross section

$$\frac{d\sigma^S}{d\Omega} = \frac{\alpha^2 \beta_\tau}{8s\beta_e} \left[(s_- - s_+)_x X_- + (s_- + s_+)_y Y_+ + (s_- - s_+)_z Z_- \right]. \quad (5)$$

Here, the coefficients X_- , Y_+ , and Z_- encapsulate the dependence on $\text{Im}(F_{2,3} F_i^*)$, with $i = 1, 2$; their explicit forms are detailed in Ref. [1]. To isolate these effects, we define the normal asymmetry, A_N^\pm , which exploits the azimuthal distribution of the decay products

$$A_N^\pm \equiv \frac{\sigma_L^\pm - \sigma_R^\pm}{\sigma_{\text{tot}}} = \pm \alpha_\pm \frac{\alpha^2 \pi \beta_e \beta_\tau^3 \gamma_\tau}{3s\sigma_{\text{tot}}} \text{Im}(F_2 F_1^*). \quad (6)$$

In this expression, $\sigma_{L/R}^\pm$ denote the cross sections integrated over distinct hadronic polar-angle hemispheres defined in the respective τ^\pm rest frames (see Ref. [1] for exact definitions). The factor α_\pm is the polarization analyzer, quantifying the sensitivity of a given hadronic decay channel to the τ spin orientation. An analogous asymmetry can be constructed to isolate the imaginary component of the electric dipole form factor, $F_3(s)$.

3.4 Observables with polarized beams

Constraining the real parts of the dipole form factors, $\text{Re} F_{2,3}$, necessitates the use of longitudinally polarized electron beams ($\lambda = \pm 1$), an upgrade anticipated for SuperKEKB. The inclusion of polarization introduces new helicity-dependent terms in the differential cross section

$$\frac{d\sigma^{S\lambda}}{d\Omega} = \frac{\alpha^2 \lambda \beta_\tau}{16s\beta_e} \left[(s_- + s_+)_x X_+ + (s_- - s_+)_y Y_- + (s_- + s_+)_z Z_+ \right], \quad (7)$$

where the coefficients X_+ , Y_- , and Z_+ contains this time the interferences $\text{Re}(F_{2,3} F_i^*)$, with $i = 1, 2$. We can isolate the interesting contributions by constructing the helicity difference $d\sigma_{\text{pol}}^S \equiv d\sigma^S|_{\lambda=1} - d\sigma^S|_{\lambda=-1}$. To probe the EDM, we utilize the y -dependent term to construct the polarization-dependent normal asymmetry, A_{N,F_3}^\pm . By integrating over the appropriate azimuthal regions, we obtain direct sensitivity to $\text{Re} F_3$

$$A_{N,F_3}^\pm = \pm \alpha_\pm \frac{\pi \alpha^2 \beta_\tau^2 \gamma_\tau}{2s\beta_e \sigma_{\text{tot}}} \left[\text{Re}(F_3 F_1^*) + \text{Re}(F_3 F_2^*) \right]. \quad (8)$$

Similarly, the anomalous magnetic moment is accessed via the transverse A_T^\pm (x -component) and longitudinal A_L^\pm (z -component) asymmetries. While both individually contain large Dirac form factor contributions, the specific linear combination

$$A_T^\pm - \frac{\pi}{2\gamma_\tau} A_L^\pm = \mp \alpha_\pm \frac{\pi \alpha^2 \beta_\tau^3 \gamma_\tau}{2s\beta_e \sigma_{\text{tot}}} \left[\text{Re}(F_2 F_1^*) + |F_2|^2 \right] \quad (9)$$

effectively cancels these. This observable allows for the definition of an effective form factor, $\text{Re } F_2^{\text{eff}}$, which can be directly extracted from experimental data to constrain a_τ^{BSM}

$$\text{Re } F_2^{\text{eff}} = \mp \frac{4s\beta_e \sigma_{\text{tot}}}{\pi^2 \alpha^2 \beta_\tau^3 \gamma_\tau \alpha_\pm} \left(A_T^\pm - \frac{\pi}{2\gamma_\tau} A_L^\pm \right). \quad (10)$$

3.5 Generalized observable for realistic cuts

Experimental kinematic cuts, such as the Belle II angular acceptance ($17^\circ < \theta_{\text{lab}} < 150^\circ$), break the standard longitudinal and transverse asymmetry cancellations Eq. (9), leaving unwanted residues. To restore sensitivity to $\text{Re } F_{2,3}(s)$, we introduce the cut-dependent coefficient

$$\mathcal{C}(\Theta) = \frac{\pi/2 - \Theta + \sin \Theta \cos \Theta}{\gamma_\tau \cos^2 \Theta}, \quad (11)$$

where Θ denotes the cut angle in the CM frame. This new observable, defined as $A_T^\pm - \mathcal{C}(\Theta) A_L^\pm$ (replacing the standard factor $\pi/(2\gamma_\tau)$), enforces the exact cancellation of both the Dirac form factor $|F_1|^2$ terms and the γ - Υ - Z interference contributions.

4 Results and projections for Belle II

We validated our unpolarized and longitudinally polarized matrix elements against earlier computations [63] and the amplitude generator OpenLoops [64, 65], observing full agreement. Furthermore, our numerical results for the asymmetries $A_{N,T,L}^\pm$ in the absence of cuts reproduce the analytical predictions of Ref. [28] within errors. All corresponding data, analysis codes, and plots are available at

<https://mule-tools.gitlab.io/user-library/dilepton/belleII-tau-g-2>

Under Belle II kinematic constraints ($17^\circ < \theta_{\text{lab}} < 150^\circ$) and restricting the analysis to soft photons ($E_\gamma < 50$ MeV), the observable sensitive to $\text{Re } F_2(s)$ yields $A_T^- - \frac{\pi}{2\gamma_\tau} A_L^- = 0.0253360(8)$. This result is orders of magnitude larger than expected and carries the wrong sign, a discrepancy driven by the incomplete cancellation of the dominant $|F_1|^2$ contribution. However, by employing the cut-dependent coefficient derived in Sec. 3.5 (with $\mathcal{C}(\Theta) \approx 0.6036$), the observable shifts to $A_T^- - \mathcal{C}(\Theta) A_L^- = -0.0004256(9)$, correcting the sign and successfully suppressing the value from $\mathcal{O}(10^{-2})$ to the expected $\mathcal{O}(10^{-4})$. Additionally, we find that NLO box diagrams contribute negligible $\mathcal{O}(10^{-10})$ corrections, as they effectively vanish in the asymmetry construction due to their θ -symmetry properties. Finally, we determine the normal asymmetry, sensitive to $\text{Im } F_2(s)$, to be $A_N^- = -0.0002061(8)$.

5 Conclusions and Outlook

We have presented the complete NLO QED results for polarized $e^+e^- \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$, demonstrating that a modified observable is essential to robustly cancel unwanted residues when incorporating Belle II kinematic cuts. To match the experimental potential for probing a_τ at the 10^{-6} level, this analysis must be extended to NNLO. The main challenges entail the computation of the polarized two-loop amplitudes utilizing massification and updating OpenLoops and the NTS stabilization procedure for arbitrary polarization. Finally, significant upgrades to the current generator *Tauola* are required, alongside an investigation into the necessity of treating τ decays beyond the narrow-width approximation. Work along these lines is in progress.

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